

schließt den Band.

Der prächtig mit Abbildungen versehene Band wird sicherlich noch etliche Jahre als Referenzwerk für diverse Fragestellungen dienen – zumindest, solange die Beschäftigung mit dem Islam im südostasiatischen Raum in der Islamforschung peripher bleibt.

Rüdiger Lohlker (Wien)
 ruediger.lohlker@univie.ac.at

Decharneux, Julien: *Creation and Contemplation. The Cosmology of the Qur'ān and its Late Antique Background*. Berlin: De Gruyter, 2023 (Studies in the History and Culture of the Middle East 47). 288 pp. ISBN 978-3-11-079401-4. € 109,95.

Julien Decharneux's monograph *Creation and Contemplation. The Cosmology of the Qur'ān and Its Late Antique Background* stands as a timely and comprehensive study of a rich selection of late antique sources. Drawing from revisions of his doctoral dissertation, the monograph focuses particularly on Christian Syriac texts, though Decharneux occasionally also refers to Jewish sources to skillfully demonstrate that whereas the Qur'ān refrains from quoting any Biblical phrases or Christian theological texts related to cosmology, it indeed echoes late antique theological debates. In so doing, the author extracts important continuities and discontinuities between Qur'ānic verses and late antique texts on cosmology.

The work analyzes the Qur'ānic cosmological thought in six chapters with a particular focus on the study of "creation" and "contemplation," seen by the author as central concepts to convey the Qur'ān's all-embracing theological claim about the existence of one God, the sole Creator and guiding power of the universe (pp. 1–2). As Decharneux persuasively argues, while the Qur'ān repeatedly invites humans to contemplate the universe "as a created entity" and thereby, perceives God in it, the holy book of Islam also employs some doctrinal arguments for the divine origin and guidance of the world (p. 2). Methodologically, the scholar discards the traditional chronology of the Qur'ān, its division in Meccan and Medinan suras, and Muslim exegesis. Moreover, he considers the Qur'ān as consisting of various layers of different authors, scribes, and compilers (p. 4). By analyzing the relevant Qur'ānic verses in light of late antique texts, Decharneux assumes that some "contributors" to the Qur'ān possessed knowledge of Christian and particularly Syriac theological debates prior to the dawn of Islam.

Chapter One focuses on an active contemplation of God's signs (*āyāt*) in the cosmos, through which believers can gain knowledge about God and His plan for the universe. Here, the author proposes that the relevant Qur'ānic verses echo the texts of the East Syrian school (pp. 16–54). Chapter Two proceeds by exploring the role of humans as contemplators and perceivers of divine signs. He investigates motifs and terms such as healing the heart, remembering God, seeking the

face of God, and knowing the limit of one's knowledge. Decharneux then traces these motifs and terms back to the East Syriac ascetic school (pp. 55–98). Chapter Three turns to the doctrine of creation and argues that despite the fact that the Qur'ān constantly reinforces the presentation of God as the only Creator of the universe and uses some well-known late antique rhetorical arguments to challenge the views of opponents, it shows no awareness of major cosmological topics debated at that time (pp. 99–142). Chapter Four explores the continuous maintenance of the universe according to the Qur'ān, supporting God's supremacy over the universe. Decharneux connects the motifs related to this doctrine (e.g., a sky without columns) especially to the homilies of the West Syrian theologian, Jacob of Sarug (pp. 143–171). While Chapter Five follows the creation of heaven and its structure (pp. 172–211), Chapter Six concludes the analysis by exploring the creation of angels and humankind (pp. 212–246). All three 'creations' (i.e., of heaven, angels, and humans) display similarities to the Biblical exegesis, while significantly departing in some parts from previous Jewish and Christian traditions.

The study's core analysis stands on firm ground based on supporting evidence, but a few interpretative positions by the author are worth a closer look. For instance, Decharneux suggests that *al-shajar* in Q 55:6 is "allegedly the tree of knowledge" and translates it as "the tree" (pp. 206, 208). Yet, the Qur'ān only mentions the one tree in Paradise – the Tree of Eternity appearing as *al-shajara* or *shajarat al-khuldi* (Q 2:35, 7:19, 7:20, 7:22, 20:120). Moreover, the wording of the verse – *wa-l-najmu wa-l-shajaru yusjidān* in Q 55:6 – makes a "symmetrical" reading more plausible. In other words, since *al-najm* refers to the stars collectively, *al-shajar* might designate "the trees" as well. This translation is supported by other Qur'ānic verses such as Q 16:68 and 22:18, in which the word – *al-shajar* – clearly denotes "the trees." Again, due to a symmetrical reading, one may identify these trees as the trees of Paradise (the stars and the trees of Paradise). The reference to these celestial objects in Q 55:6 will be in accordance with Q 55:5 and 55:7 and contrast the objects on earth in Q 55:10–12. Although the Qur'ān does not explicitly mention the trees in Paradise elsewhere, it frequently speaks of the shade and various fruits (e.g., Q 4:57, 77:41, 55:52, 55:68), which supports the reading of *al-shajar* in Q 55:6 as the trees of Paradise. More importantly, one may also challenge Decharneux's interpretation of Q 55:8–9 being a later interpolation (pp. 205–210). Based on my reading, God's creation of the earth for all living creatures or humans and the elaboration about the merits of the earth as offering its fruits, date palms, and so on in Q 55:11–12 presumably to the living creatures is counterbalanced with the elaboration on the scale (*al-mīzān*) in Q 55:8–9. The verses, Q 55:8–9 link the scale to humans as well. While God creates the firmament as the scale in the universe, humans are supposed to establish the weight in justice and not to transgress regarding the scale (of justice). In other words, the use of the scale cosmologically and ethically looks intentional in

my view.

In the process of analyzing angels as part of God's creation, Decharneux connects the cherubs to those Qur'ānic angels who are near God (*muqarrabūna*). He explains *muqarrabūna* and the root *q-r-b* as the Qur'ān's deformation or distortion of the Hebrew and Syriac words *kerūbīm/krūbē* and the root *k-r-b* to give a new meaning to the name of angels (pp. 220–221). Yet, not only Jesus is depicted as *muqarrabuna* (Q 3:45), as he correctly notes, but also the believers of the first group in Paradise, i.e., the forerunners in faith are described as *muqarrabūna* (Q 56:11 and 56:88). Therefore, it seems more plausible to consider *muqarrabūna* as the genuine Qur'ānic Arabic term designating those who dwell in presence of God such as (some) angels, Jesus, and the forerunners in faith, rather than a distortion of the term cherubs broadening its meaning from cherubs to the believers with a special merit.

On a side note, the transcription of Syriac is generally challenging and the monograph contains minor errors: e.g., *neqrā* ("he might read openly") instead of *neqrē* on p. 52, *ayk* ("like") instead of *ak* (/y/is not pronounced) on p. 161, *d-laweh* ("on which"+ suffix 3p.m. sg.) instead of *da-law* on the same page, or *kawkabē* instead of *kawkbē* on p. 184.

Overall, Decharneux pays close and important attention to a set of underinvestigated topics in Qur'ānic studies, making his study a valuable contribution to a rapidly expanding research subfield. Future scholars will certainly draw on this detailed study and consider it as an essential reading for a better understanding of Qur'ānic cosmology.

Ana Davitashvili¹ (University of Tübingen)
Ana.davitashvili@uni-tuebingen.de

Frembgen, Jürgen Wasim: *Magie und Ekstase. Kleine Kulturgeschichte des unbekanntes Islam*. Freiburg & Basel & Wien: Herder Verlag, 2022. ISBN Print 978-3-451-39416-4. € 16,00; ISBN E-Book (EPUB) 978-3-451-82874-4. € 11,99; ISBN E-Book (PDF) 978-3-451-82883-6 € 11,99.

Der Titel dieses Buches mag Assoziationen des Exotischen oder sogar Esoterischen wecken – doch es ist der Untertitel, der ankündigt, worum es wirklich geht, und der Inhalt hält in einer gut lesbaren und übersichtlich strukturierten Form, was da versprochen wird.

Den Ethnologen und Islamwissenschaftler Jürgen Wasim Frembgen interessieren speziell die Ausdrucksformen muslimischer Volksfrömmigkeit, die kaum unter dem Label „der Islam“ bekannt sind und nicht selten synkretistische Ele-

¹ This review is part of a project that has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement ID: 866043).